

Analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional
system for Sensing the Environment

Project Identity Manual

Deliverable No.	D1.3		
Due Date	30.11.2016		
Submission Date	30.11.2016		
Deliverable Leader	SUPSI		
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	PP	Restricted to other project participants (including R4D services)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
Status	to be continuously updated		

Change log

Version	Date	Amended by	Changes
1.0	29.11.2016	M. Cannata	Document finalized for submission

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
1.0	IST-SUPSI	Massimiliano Cannata, Daniele Strigaro

NOTES:

For comments / suggestions / contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4onse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch

For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

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1 Executive summary

This document describes the corporate identity which has been developed for the 4nse project. The corporate identity consists of logo for the overall project and templates for written and presentation materials and printed communication materials.

2 Material and Methods

In order to build a recognisable identity for the project, a complete style – including logos and communication templates – has been developed that encompasses the entire width of the project. The corporate identity has been designed to ensure that communication and design are consistent and recognisable, thereby contributing to the possible impact of the project. The corporate identity is implemented in all dissemination activities, both internally and externally, and all other forms of communication.

The corporate identity serves as a red thread through the project, not only bringing it together but also making outcomes more easily identifiable and their position within the overall programme of the research project more clear.

The 4nse corporate identity consists of:

- Project logo
- Project font
- Templates (letters, reporting and presentation)
- Printed communication materials
 - Business card of the project events containing general contact information

2.1 Logos of the project

All communication from and within the project will have the same, uniform lay-out, use of logo and colours. Following logo was developed for the project:

The project's logo reflects the acronym of the project and reuse the logo of the famous © Marvel Comics characters "Fantastic Four" available in Public Domain (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Fantastic_Four_logo.svg) to underline how the four openness of the project may lead to fantastic impacts.

Apart from the above official logo, a other of different versions has been designed to permit usage in different contexts.

	Project logo
	Negative project logo (*)
	Iconized project logo
	Iconized negative project logo (*)

(*) the black color is actually transparent

2.2 Project font

In all the documents and project communication material the selected font is “Armata” for heading styles while Open Sans for Body styles. Armata is a low contrast sans serif text face available with Open Font License. Open Sans was optimized for print, web, and mobile interfaces, and has excellent legibility characteristics in its letterforms; it is available with Apache License, Version 2.0. The True Type Font files for installation are available in the B2DROP sharing storage.

Google Fonts

DIRECTORY FEATURED ABOUT

Armata + SELECT THIS FONT

Glyph

Aa

Characters

ABCĆČDĎEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSŠTUVWXYZŽabcč
 ěďđefghijklmnopqrsštuvwxyzž1234567890'?
 "!"(%)[#]{}@/&<-+÷×=>@!\$€£¥¢;:,.*

Designer

 Viktoriya Grabowska
Principal design

Styles

Type here to preview text 40px

Regular

About

Armata is a low contrast sans serif text face, with a mixture of familiar and unfamiliar shapes. The steadiness and strength is juxtaposed with some innovative and delicate gestures. Armata can be used in a wide range of sizes.

Popular Pairings with Armata

	+	<p style="font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold;">The spectacle before us was indeed sublime.</p> <p>Apparently we had reached a great height in the atmosphere, for the sky was a dead black, and the stars had ceased to twinkle. By the same illusion which lifts the horizon of</p>
	+	
	+	

Usage

These are the countries where Armata is most

2.3 Letter, Reports and Presentation template

Templates for the different activities have been developed in order to unify the public presentation of the project by project partners during dissemination activities. All the templates are available on the B2DROP file sharing storage and shall be used by the project partners. They have received instructions on using them for all dissemination activities and report writing. The partners are responsible for reporting in English, but might there be any reporting or distribution of materials in any other, the specific partner will take care of modify the existing template accordingly. The templates are shown in Annexes of this document.

The deliverable should have the following structure:

1. Executive Summary (max. one page)
2. Material and Methods (the report main content)
3. Deviation from work plan (if and why)
4. Conclusions (max. one or two page)
5. References (list of citations)

2.4 Communication materials

The printed communication materials will be used especially for promoting the events and attracting stakeholders. These can serve as a convenient and easy way to spread the information on 4onse events between relevant stakeholders.

2.5 Social media

The project has activated a twitter account (https://twitter.com/SNSF_4onse), a LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8579328>) and a gitHub repository (<https://github.com/4onse/>).

2.6 Website

The project website has been created and published. It is accessible at the URL: www.4onse.ch and www.4onse.org. The website has been created in a responsive technologies that make it readable on every device.

The website sections are:

- Home
- Project (Introduction, Governance, Working packages, case study)
- Outreach (Presentations, Videos, Materials)
- Results
- Cooperation
- Links

3 Deviation from Work Plan

No deviation from the work plan.

4 Conclusions

The project identity has been designed and relative templates are available to all the partners. Together, the elements of the 4onse corporate identity (will) result in a coherent presentation of the 4onse project and its activities.

Appendix B Reporting template

4nse: analysis of Four-times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

[Title]

Deliverable-No.	DX
Due-Date	DD.MM.YYYY
Submission-Date	DD.MM.YYYY
Deliverable-Leader	SUPSI-/UOM-/IST-/UGM
Dissemination-Level	PU Public
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	RE Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D-services)
	CO Confidential only for project and the R4D-services
Status	to be continuously updated

4nse project has been fund within the Research for Development program with decision: IZ07Z010906 / 1

[Title]

Change-log

Version	Date	Amended-by	Changes
0.1	DD-MM-YYYY		
1.0			
1.1			

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner-Name	People-involved
0.1		
1.0		
1.1		

NOTES

For comments/suggestions/contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4nse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch
 For more information on the project 4nse, link to <http://www.4nse.ch>

Page Break

Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0

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[Title]

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[Title]

Executive summary

Euse ultricies vehicula ligula ornare dictum. Phasellus volutpat vitae justo porttitor sollicitudin. Vivamus faucibus odio dui. Quisque laoreet nunc sit amet nisi tempus pretium. Mauris vestibulum mattis dui, nec consequat massa bibendum at. Integer posuere tellus ut posuere laoreet, integer quam massa placerat nec ullamcorper a, ultrices vel sem. Morbi pellentesque a elit nec tincidunt. Donec id porttitor ante. Aenean maximus lacina metus vitae ornare. Sed efficitur nulla nisi, et maximus orci consequat ac.

1 → Introduction (Heading1-style)

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Etiam ac eros nisi. In tristique, nunc tempus enim pellentesque, a, egestas augue tincidunt. Donec, laboris, fermentum dictum. Etiam suscipit, leo, turpis, id semper tortor molestie nec. Morbi gravida condimentum nunc, id molestie justo porttitor id. Suspendisse vel risus non ipsum ornare posuere. Quisque in lacinia mauris, vitae molestie mi. Suspendisse ac mi dignissim eros malesuada scelerisque sed et nisi.

Figure 1-xxx

Morbi elit metus, interdum vel ante ac, placerat pellentesque mi. Duis ultricies nulla condimentum, laoreet lectus eu, finibus est. Maecenas massa sapien, vehicula pellentesque diam et, tristique tempor tortor. Curabitur et enim a diam pulvinar finibus. Etiam tempus, lectus ut tristique vestibulum, purus urna laoreet massa, at mattis lectus quam at nisi. Ut sodales eu metus at suscipit.

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[Title]

Vestibulum porta consequat elementum. Morbi sodales, dui sit amet consectetur malesuada, nunc risus placerat tellus, eu efficitur dolor ex quis ante.

2- Material and Methods (Heading 1-style)

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2.1- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet (Heading 2-style)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Phasellus placerat rutrum diam, quis aliquam mi egestas non. Aliquam id velit magna. Ut e massa vel arcu consectetur mattis sit amet ut ex. Nulla tincidunt leo nulla, in vehicula est sollicitudin ut. Curabitur vehicula erat nec dapibus tincidunt. Vestibulum cursus interdum lobortis. Curabitur vulputate iaculis ipsum. Nulla facilisis sit amet orci in aliquam. Class aptent taciti sociosqu ad litora torquent per conubia nostra, per inceptos himenaeos. Vivamus gravida lectus nunc feugiat dictum.

Nulla facilisi. Aenean eget fermentum mauris. Phasellus ut elit vitae velit luctus tincidunt non id tellus. Nunc iaculis ultrices risus vitae porta nisi ullamcorper vel. Phasellus tincidunt lobortis hendrerit. Donec vulputate placerat eleifend. Vestibulum convallis bibendum tincidunt.

2.2- Vivamus tincidunt ex eros (Heading 2-style)

Etiam a sem libero. Pellentesque odio urna, dictum eget ipsum sed, placerat porttitor tellus. Suspendisse vitae tellus risus. Pellentesque sit amet sodales massa. Donec interdum est a felis commodo, quis interdum magna interdum. Quisque pretium sit amet arcu non rutrum. Aliquam maximus facilisis lorem in porttitor. Sed eleifend nibh nunc molestie aliquet.

Proin mauris odio, placerat sed risus eu.

- 1- Iacinia hendrerit diam.
- 2- Aliquam viverra lobortis luctus.
- 3- Suspendisse blandit vulputate nisi eget tristique.

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[Title]

3- Deviation from Work Plan (Heading 1-style)

Mauris tellus libero maximus vitae rutrum at auctor at augue. Cras velit ipsum, fermentum vel ante eu, posuere ornare neque. Praesent pellentesque cursus aliquet. Maecenas vulputate vitae erat a sollicitudin. Morbi luctus ipsum quis vulputate malesuada. Nam nec efficitur justo, ut finibus lacus. Donec ultricies augue eu nulla sagittis, id placerat nunc blandit. In mollis ex sit amet pulvinar suscipit. Aenean convallis blandit diam sed auctor.

4- Conclusions (Heading 1-style)

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References (Head Plain-style)

Use Reference Style and order alphabetically

Gore, A.: (2006). "An inconvenient truth: The planetary emergency of global warming and what we can do about it." Emmaus, PA: Rodale. x

Gore, A.: (2006). "An inconvenient truth: The planetary emergency of global warming and what we can do about it." Emmaus, PA: Rodale. x

New York State Department of Health.: (2002). "After a sexual assault." [Brochure]. Albany, NY: Author. x

Schneider, S.: H.: (2000). "Greenhouse effect." World book encyclopedia (Millennium ed. Vol. 8, pp. 382-383). Chicago, IL: World Book. x

Miller-Rushing, A.: J.; Primack, R.: B.; Primack, D.; & Mukunda, S.: (2006). "Photographs and herbarium specimens as tools to document phenological changes in response to global warming." American Journal of Botany, 93, 1667-1674. x

Appendix A -> Nunc neque eros (Appendix-style)

Praesent ut massa odio. Phasellus id interdum sem, in suscipit sem. Quisque varius posuere est, ut vestibulum lorem pulvinar vel. Aenean egestas mollis nibh in fringilla. Sed condimentum, neque eu molestie suscipit, turpis turpis cursus sem, porta rhoncus nibh lacus consequat nisi. Cras pellentesque id. Duis in vestibulum. Nunc sodales euismod mauris lobortis gravida. Aliquam erat vulputate. Phasellus mattis metus ipsum, sit amet congue eget elementum sit amet. Nam feugiat sagittis lorem euismod sagittis.

4nse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Appendix C Letter template

Project Coordination:
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University of Applied Sciences and Arts
of Southern Switzerland

SUPSI

Analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Supsi is a project funded within the "Research for Development program" (with decision 020702/102806 /1)

P.P. SUPSI, IST 04-0932 Canobbio

Dear TITLE
NAME SURNAME
c/o Ademar
ADDRESS
POSTCODE CITY

name surname
T +39 02 90 000 00 00
XXXXXXXXXXXX@xxxx.xxx

Location date
initial name/cognome
initial name/cognome

Subject of the communication

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Mauris elementum, mi sollicitudin laoreet eleifend, libero ligula congue justo, id feugiat augue magna porttitor mi. Praesent ullamcorper sit amet massa in dapibus. Nulla viverra diam ut nibh vestibulum, non vulputate ipsum mattis. Cras eget varius orci. In ac semper eros. Pellentesque nec risus non eros mollis egestas nec non dolor. Vestibulum aliquet massa odio, vel vehicula magna dictum nec. Nulla dictum, arcu eu semper dapibus, lorem sem pharetra ipsum, in blandit lorem dui sed odio. Etiam eleifend gravida tortor ac gravida. Vestibulum rhoncus ultricies sem, vel posuere magna tempor sit amet. Vestibulum non rhoncus neque, id accumsan arcu. Aliquam vitae sem facilisis, euismod elit vel, cursus ex. Sed sollicitudin dignissim erat sed tempus. Morbi hendrerit purus vitae finibus rhoncus. Suspendisse potenti.

Praesent eget porta purus, eu rutrum augue. Quisque ultricies dolor ac orci malesuada semper. Nulla id vulputate enim. Nulla mattis dui at felis consequat malesuada. Sed vitae odio rutrum, vulputate est non, iaculis enim. Vivamus dui lorem, condimentum sit amet mauris ac, elementum tempor sem.

Page 2 of 2

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Sed fermentum urna convallis, congue arcu sit amet, accumsan libero. Mauris tellus justo, vestibulum at consectetur eget, tempor ut lectus. Praesent sit amet ex quis enim ultricies blandit eget et nunc. Quisque in nunc sit amet tortor imperdiet aliquet ut ac augue. Quisque vestibulum, lectus id laoreet dignissim, diam nibh suscipit lorem, vitae mollis libero lectus eget nulla. Nullam tincidunt commodo scelerisque. Fusce pretium, leo consectetur finibus bibendum, lectus ex finibus quam, non maximus metus risus et quam. Phasellus metus enim, semper ac efficitur quis, tincidunt a massa. Donec tristique elit felis, nec viverra purus dignissim quis.

Aliquam quis lacus nisi. Sed dapibus dignissim odio id convallis. Aliquam faucibus tortor non risus fringilla pellentesque vel at neque. Fusce auctor id mi sed scelerisque. Vestibulum tristique malesuada aliquet. Proin nec aliquet mi. Nam quis augue sagittis, finibus nibh vel, tempus lacus. Etiam vel ullamcorper purus, id pellentesque lorem. Proin sollicitudin nulla eu justo scelerisque, ullamcorper lacinia dolor faucibus. Cras consequat dictum dictum. Donec vel arcu scelerisque, vehicula eros sed, scelerisque ligula. Aliquam ipsum leo, commodo ultricies odio non, pretium sollicitudin elit. Maecenas venenatis urna ac erat lobortis vulputate.

Nunc eu congue dui. Vestibulum at ullamcorper ligula, sit amet dictum elit. Cras nec turpis at mauris bibendum dignissim. Class aptent taciti sociosqu ad litora torquent per conubia nostra, per inceptos himenaeos. Fusce pulvinar orci orci, nec dignissim leo sagittis aliquet. Sed vitae feugiat sapien. Nullam eget turpis vitae velit tristique bibendum. Vestibulum cursus mattis eros sit amet lacinia. Phasellus felis nulla, tempus eget ante tempor, finibus pharetra enim. Quisque porttitor varius tortor, sed rhoncus nunc varius ut. Etiam lacus turpis, dapibus consectetur dapibus sit amet, luctus vel ligula. Morbi scelerisque id dolor eu tincidunt.

Analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Appendix D Presentation template

Title Layout

Title and Content layout

Section Header layout

Concluding layout